

Fast Fashion– A Destructive Loop of Overconsumption

Tithi Mitra & Sankar Roy Maulik*

Department of Silpa-Sadana, Visva-Bharati University, Sriniketan, India

Abstract

Textiles play a significant role in our daily life. In addition to serving the basic requirements, textiles are increasingly becoming a fashion statement as they spread across society. The fashion industry is one of the biggest polluters in terms of waste generation, resource utilization, and consumption of water. Hence, there is a need for a fundamental fashion business model, that includes sustainable practices throughout the supply chain and an increasing product life cycle. It also deals with the conscious choices made by the consumer while purchasing. There are two competing ways to look at the fashion industry: slow and fast. Slow fashion emphasizes high-quality, timeless designs and ecological and ethical business practices, whereas fast fashion is characterized by cheap, fashionable, and disposable apparel developed fast and marketed at low prices. In the current era, overexposure to the newest fashion trends has resulted in an inclination towards fast fashion, which is connected to several environmental issues, including resource consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, land usage, landfills, soil degradation and deforestation, excessive water consumption, air pollution, microfibre pollution, packaging pollution, etc. The inclination towards fast fashion is mainly due to the use of social media and digital marketing. This paper provides an analysis of the relationship between fast fashion and its environmental issues.

Keywords: *Consumer, Environment, Fashion, Greenwashing, Micro-fibre, Pollution*

*Corresponding Author:

Dr Sankar Roy Maulik

Associate Professor

Department of Silpa-Sadana

Visva-Bharati (A Central University)

Sriniketan - 731236

E-mails: s_r_moulik@yahoo.co.in / sankar.raymaulik@visva-bharati.ac.in

1. Introduction

The role of textiles in our daily lives is enormous. As textiles become more ubiquitous, they are not only fulfilling the basic needs of mankind but are also becoming a fashion statement. Fashion can be defined as the expression of aesthetic values at a specific time and place. It reflects a particular period's social, economic, and artistic expressions through clothing, footwear, accessories, makeup, and lifestyle. There is an interconnection between fashion and style. To become a fashion, the audience must widely accept a style. Fashion is a dynamic concept characterized by change occurring in a general direction. These changes are termed trends. In the current era, a tendency towards fast fashion has arisen due to excessive exposure to the latest fashion trends.

Human activities have a broad and varied impact on the environment. There are several ways in which the human race contributes to the degradation of the environment; one of these is through the fast fashion industry. Fashion is one of the world's largest, most globalized, and most important industries. Fast fashion is typically a business model that deals with trendy, easily accessible clothing intended to endure only a few uses before being discarded in a landfill. A fast fashion product leaves a pollution footprint at every stage of its life cycle, from fiber production to post-consumer disposal. Figure 1 depicts different fibers used in textiles and fashion. This study thoroughly analyses the relationship between fashion and its environmental effects.

Researchers have discussed and reported the environmental impacts concerning the textile and fashion value chain [1]. Rukhaya et al. analyzed and reported sustainable approaches and alternatives to fast fashion [2]. Researchers investigated and discussed different dimensions of slow fashion and its versatility [3]. Researchers hypothesized that clothing libraries could promote a longer service life for clothes, reducing the fast production of garments, and also analyzed and reviewed the environmental impact of the textile supply

chain [4]. Roy Choudhury discussed in his paper the importance of a textile product's Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to examine the textile industry's environmental impacts [5]. Petroody et al. reported that most microplastics found in water treatment plants were microfibres, of which polyester microfibres were the most abundant, followed by polyamide and acrylic microfibres [6]. Researchers examine the relationships between positive or negative social media communications, fashion-conscious consumers, and purchase intentions. Consumer purchasing behaviour was found to be strongly influenced by social media [7].

Figure 1: The fiber used in textile and fashion

2. Fast and Slow Fashion

The term ‘fast fashion’ refers to a method for manufacturing and marketing fashion garments that focuses on making the latest trends available to consumers quickly and at an affordable price. The globalization of fashion trends has facilitated the rapid growth of this industry. Typically, fast fashion collection ideas are derived from the runway shows of luxurious brands. This business strategy allows mainstream consumers to purchase the latest fashions in an affordable way [2].

Textile manufacturing has increased dramatically due to global population expansion and fast fashion. Fashion is one of the most polluting industries, accounting for 8% of total carbon emissions and 20% of world wastewater [8]. The fashion sector generates more carbon emissions than international aircraft and shipping, consuming around 93 billion cubic meters of water annually. Figure 2 shows the impact on the environment of the textile and apparel industry.

Figure 2: Environmental impact of the textile and apparel industry

The slow fashion movement promotes a more ethical and environmentally friendly method of clothing manufacture and consumption. It encourages people to invest in well-made, long-lasting clothing by emphasizing quality above quantity. Slow fashion prioritizes waste and environmental impact reduction and the promotion of ethical work practices in contrast to the fast fashion sector, which is characterized by quick style changes and inexpensive labour and materials. This could include using production methods that use the least amount of water, energy, and sustainable materials, such as organic cotton or recycled textiles. In addition, slow fashion strongly emphasizes supply chain transparency, guaranteeing that employees receive fair compensation and work in safe and healthy environments [9].

Although fast fashion allows consumers to buy more clothes for less money, it also impacts the environment. It creates possible occupational and environmental hazards at every stage of the clothing life cycle. Numerous environmental problems are linked to fast fashion, including resource consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, land use, landfills, soil degradation and deforestation, excessive water consumption, air pollution, microfibre pollution, packaging pollution, etc. [2]. The fashion industry is estimated to use large amounts of water, averaging 200 metric tonnes while producing one tonne of textile [1]. The garment sector affects local water resources by generating wastewater, which goes beyond aggravating water scarcity. Untreated wastewater that reaches the local groundwater might harm the entire ecosystem since some of the chemicals used in production are poisonous. The most greenhouse gases are produced per unit of material by textiles. Over 15,000 different chemicals are used by the textile industry during manufacturing, starting with the synthesis of fibers [1]. According to estimates, cotton crops consume 6% of global pesticide production, including 16% of insecticides, 4% of herbicides, growth regulators, and defoliants, and 1% of fungicides. Agrochemical use can contribute to nausea, diarrhoea, cancers, and respiratory diseases. At the same time, acute pesticide poisoning is responsible for nearly 1,000 deaths a day and affects neurological and reproductive problems, such as infertility, miscarriage, and birth defects [1]. Fast fashion production and consumption have dramatically increased, which has led to a rise in textile waste. Pre-consumer waste in the fashion industry, also known as production waste, is created during the production of textiles and apparel. It comprises waste from manufacturing fiber, yarn, and fabric [1]. In the past few years, significant focus has been placed on a pre-consumer waste category known as 'deadstock'. It describes products or inventories that have not been sold and are no longer required by the manufacturer, distributor, or retailer. Various factors can lead to deadstock, including overproduction, cancellations, or changes in design and trend.

3. Fibre to Fashion

The textile industry consists of natural fibers (such as wool, silk, cotton, linen, hemp, etc.) and man-made fibers (subdivided into regenerated, synthetic, inorganic, etc.). The most common are synthetic fibers derived from petrochemicals, such as polyamide, polyester, and acrylic. Synthetic fibers are becoming the fashion industry's one of the miracle solutions. As a result of their affordability, durability, and ability to be manipulated, these fibers are popular with fast fashion companies [2]. Over the last two decades, the production of fibers for textile manufacturing has doubled, while the population has only risen by 25%. This significant boost in fiber production is evidence of the growing demand for textiles worldwide. It highlights the importance of the textile industry as a key player in the global economy [10].

3.1 Pollution through Polyester Value Chain

The traditional polyester garment value chain includes several sectors. These include textile manufacturers who produce polyester fabrics, apparel manufacturers who create the clothing, wholesalers who distribute the garments to retailers, and retailers who sell the clothing to consumers. Each industry is essential in bringing these polyester garments to market, ultimately providing consumers with diverse and fashionable clothing options.

The value chain starts in the oil sector since it obtains and refines crude oil to provide the fundamental elements that the chemical industry uses to make PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate) and other chemicals. The chemical industry supplies PET chips to the textile sector, where they are processed and extruded into fibers and yarns. Through professional knitting or weaving processes, these yarns are subsequently utilized to produce high-quality textiles. Incorporating dyes and chemicals is essential to achieving specific qualities in fibers and textiles [10]. These processes need extensive energy, and improper waste handling in the supply chain may pollute the land and the water. Direct release of chemical or dye effluent into adjacent bodies of water causes environmental hazards. Microfibres are discharged into the atmosphere while making textile articles from polyester fiber and remain there as particulates in the air. Due to daily exposure to hazardous compounds, including microfibres, synthetic dyes, and petrochemicals, factory employees are at significant risk of developing health issues. Asthma, lung infections, and allergies are more common due to this exposure, which can happen by inhalation or skin contact. The dyeing and finishing of textile products are responsible for around 20% of the world's water contamination [10]. The chemicals used to produce textiles include detergents, flame retardants, stain repellents, softeners, careers, etc. The residues of these substances, often not biodegradable, may be released into the environment, where they are likely to propagate and possibly reach the food chain [10]. Avoiding hazardous chemicals during the finishing process will increase

the sustainability of textiles and adhere to circular design concepts by allowing garments to be recycled without contaminating recycling systems.

The various stages of the textile value chain are commonly executed in various countries or regions. For instance, oil is extracted in one location and transferred to another for refining and producing chemicals like PET since not all countries have oil reserves. The PET chips can be sent back to a different site to be transformed into fibers and yarns, then transported to a different place to be converted into fabrics. These are then delivered to many destinations so retail stores can purchase them. Global warming has been accelerated by the significant carbon footprint created by transporting raw materials, fibers and yarns, textiles, clothing, and all the chemicals required at each stage [10].

The term 'carbon footprint' refers to the total amount of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide, that one person, organization, action, event, or product emits throughout its lifespan. Carbon dioxide accounts for roughly 80% of industrialized emissions and is the primary root cause of global warming. The primary cause of carbon footprints is the combustion of fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and natural gas, which emit CO₂ into the atmosphere. Deforestation, industrial processes, agriculture, and transportation contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. The textile business emits considerable amounts of CO₂ during its entire lifecycle, including raw material production, manufacture, transportation, and waste disposal.

Environmental sustainability may be made possible by considering the whole life cycle of textiles, starting with the design and material procurement process. Regarding carbon emissions, the term 'carbon neutrality' describes a situation where there is no net release of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions into the atmosphere. It is accomplished when a unit, such as an organization, community, or nation, balances the quantity of CO₂ it emits and the amount of CO₂ that is removed proportionately.

3.2 Microfibre Pollution

Since the discovery of microplastics (tiny particles ranging in size between 5 mm to microns), much effort has been made to research the issues. Like bigger plastic particles, microplastics are made of polymers such as polyethylene, polystyrene, etc. Various researchers have attempted several studies to determine the quantity of microplastic particles in a body of water. The outcome reveals that microplastics may be found almost everywhere, even in deep-sea trenches, and according to them, most microplastics found in water are microfibrils [11]. Each year, the amount of microfibrils released into the ocean varies from 2 million, with approximately 700,000 microfibrils escaping through washing machines [12]. Microfibrils can be released into the environment through synthetic fiber production, use, and disposal. These microfibrils harm marine life because they are eaten by fish and other species in marine ecosystems [13].

3.3 Marine Impact of Fast Fashion

By discharging microfibrils into the environment, fast fashion adversely affects marine life. During washing, polyester, nylon, and acrylic release microfibrils that may harm marine life in waterbodies and oceans. Microfibrils can impact marine life in several ways, some of which are listed below:

- Marine species, such as fish and shellfish, can consume microfibrils after mistaking them for food. This can lead to digestive issues, starvation, and even death.
- During their journey from the sea to the land, microfibrils can accumulate in the bodies of marine animals. This can lead to toxic effects as they reach higher levels of the food chain.
- In addition to destroying coral reefs, microfibrils contribute to a decline in biodiversity and ecosystem loss.

4. The Psychology of Fast Fashion

Psychological factors play a significant role in fast fashion, which depends on a range of factors that drive consumer behaviour and contribute to the growth of this business model. The desire for novelty and trendiness among consumers drives fast fashion. Consumers frequently become attracted to it because it delivers a steady supply of fresh trends and patterns, which can create a sense of excitement and expectation.

4.1 Role of Social Media and Advertisement in Fast Fashion

Increasing social media use and website advertising have heavily commercialized this fashion form. In several ways, social media has contributed significantly to the growing popularity of fast fashion [7]. For fast fashion businesses, social media networks like Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, and TikTok have made it easy for them to promote their exclusive products and instantly reach a large audience.

Fast fashion clothing is promoted and worn by influencers and celebrities who have large followers, which generates interest and buzz about the brand. People want to keep up with the newest trends and flaunt their fashion choices on social media, creating a culture of instant satisfaction. Additionally, social media gives fast fashion brands immediate feedback on their products. It allows them to reach a much wider audience with a few clicks, enabling them to sell their products worldwide [14].

The popularity of fashion hauls has increased in recent years due to the growth of social media and influencer marketing. A 'fashion haul' is a video or blog post on social media showing people their latest purchase from an apparel shop or online market. Usually, the content maker displays each item they bought, tries it on, and provides feedback on how well it fits and looks. Hence, many fashion hauls promote the most recent trends and guide viewers to frequently update their wardrobes, contributing to a society that embraces fast fashion.

The targeted advertisement also plays a vital role in the growth of fast fashion consumption. Using data and insights on users' behaviour, interests, demographics, and other factors, targeted advertising shows more relevance to selected consumers than showing identical advertisements to everyone. User data, including search queries, browsing histories, social media activity, and purchase histories, is gathered and analyzed for targeted advertising. Providing fashion buyers with more information about brands and product purchase decisions that influence them might cause excessive consumption of fashion garments.

5. Growth of E-Commerce

The term 'e-commerce' refers to the exchange of products and services through the Internet. Online shopping has drastically changed the clothing purchasing pattern due to its convenience and accessibility. E-commerce has complex environmental effects since it reduces emissions in some areas while increasing emissions in others. Shopping online provides consumers with an endless selection of products much more quickly and efficiently than possible in a physical store; also, with this shopping experience, consumers can learn more about their products by reading descriptions and reviews. One significant advantage of online shopping is the convenience of browsing from home or while traveling and making purchases at any time. Additionally, e-commerce has reduced production costs for fast fashion brands by reducing their dependence on physical stores. All these factors contribute to the growth of overconsumption of fast fashion products. For faster delivery, companies often divide orders and ship them separately instead of together, increasing packaging and transportation costs and carbon emissions. The packaging of products, including the shipping containers for online orders, accounts for 29.8% of waste in the United States, or 75 million tons. Many materials are not recyclable [15].

6. Sustainable Consumption of Textiles

Choosing more responsible and conscious choices when purchasing, using, and disposing of textiles and fashion garments is one way to ensure sustainable consumption. Investing in durable, long-lasting, sustainable garments can reduce the need to replace garments. Many natural, sustainable fabrics from natural fibers such as organic cotton, linen, hemp, and bamboo are available to consumers. These natural fabrics are eco-friendly to produce and use. A great way to reduce the demand for new clothing is by purchasing second-hand clothing or using clothing libraries.

Using the earth's resources more judiciously is a necessity without question. Significant environmental issues caused by the current business model include deforestation, loss of biodiversity, and an increase in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission and pollution. Several concepts for an environmentally friendly future emphasize reducing, recycling, and reusing to reduce the industry's environmental impact. The transition to a more sustainable fashion industry, for instance, could involve a business model where society switches from a take-make-dispose economy to a circular economy that aims to keep all resources or products in the system for as long as possible to reduce end-of-life textile waste [8].

It is possible to extend the useful life of a discarded garment by transferring it to a new owner via second-hand stores or charities when it is still wearable. The garments can also be diversified into something new and useful.

7. Consequences of Greenwashing

Greenwashing, or misleading claims about sustainability to boost a brand's reputation [10]. Even if their products or activities are not, brands may utilize greenwashing market strategies to give the impression that the products are eco-friendly or sustainable. Greenwashing may take many forms, including the vague or intangible use of phrases like 'eco-friendly' or 'sustainable' without any additional information on the environmental effect of the item or service. Even if a product has minimal or no link to the natural world, companies may employ deceptive visuals to suggest that it is environmentally friendly, such as images of wildlife or natural landscapes. Another common approach is to highlight the insignificant environmental aspects of a product while ignoring or underestimating its more important environmental effects or to do so by utilizing false or unrelated certifications or labels to suggest that a product is environmentally friendly.

Both the environment and customers may suffer highly as a result of greenwashing. Companies may destroy consumer trust and make it more difficult for customers to make knowledgeable choices by misleading them about the environmental effects of their activities or products. Greenwashing also makes it more difficult for customers to differentiate between real environmental claims and marketing hype, which may harm the efforts of businesses dedicated to sustainability and environmental responsibility. Identification must be strictly governed to prevent this problem and maintain eco-labeling reliability. In addition, clothing retailers should support sustainability and incorporate educational content to reassure consumers that they are getting a good deal when purchasing items with an eco-label [10].

7.1 Global Regulatory Body

Understanding of safety requirements of textiles and apparel are essential to protect consumers and the environment from the harmful effect of restricted substances. Generally, a restricted substance must be absent from a finished product or present at a limited concentration. Some substances are restricted due to environmental concerns, while others are restricted due to health and safety concerns for workers or consumers. The Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) is a measure for promoting social accountability and ecologically responsible manufacturing practices worldwide. It includes all aspects of producing, modifying, manufacturing, packaging, labeling, exporting, importing, and distributing all-natural fibers. GOTS establishes strict environmental standards for the manufacture of textiles. Heavy metals, hazardous chemicals, and genetically modified organisms are all forbidden; any packaging made of PVC is prohibited. Along with encouraging trash reduction and recycling, it also enforces appropriate water and energy usage. As part of its supply chain, GOTS takes social factors into account. The International Labour Organisation conventions must be followed, particularly those that forbid child and forced labour. It guarantees a right to wage negotiation, secure working conditions, and appropriate wages. A product must be 67% recyclable or biodegradable to receive Cradle-to-Cradle (C2C) certification. REACH is the European Community Regulation on chemicals and their safe use. It refers to the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of chemicals. REACH aims to improve the protection of human health and the environment through better and early identification of chemical substances. The OEKO-TEX is an independent third-party certifier that offers OEKO-TEX 100 for products and OEKO-TEX 1000 for production sites/factories. Textiles considered for this standard are classified into four categories: Product Class I: products for babies; Product Class II: products with direct contact with skin; Product Class III: Products without direct contact with skin and Product Class IV: decoration materials. The Global Recycled Standard (GRS) is a holistic certification for products with recycled content, whereas the Recycled Content Standard (RCS) applies to products that contain 5%–100% recycled material. Other examples of different certifications are SMART (Sustainable Materials Rating Technology), GreenGuard, Consumer Product Safety Act, Environmental Protection Agency, Eco-Mark Scheme of India, ISO 14000 Series, etc.

7.2 Government policies

The environmentally harmful supply chain operations of the fashion industry are now coming under increased global scrutiny. However, the industry continues to expand despite widely publicized criticism over its limited consideration of social and environmental issues. It is estimated that the industry produces 8-10% of global CO₂ emissions and is also a major consumer of water, responsible for ~20% of industrial water pollution, and contributes ~35% of oceanic primary microplastic pollution [16]. The environmental impact of the textile and apparel industry clearly explains that one kilogram of fabric uses 2,000 litres of water and 4 kilowatt hours of energy which generates 23 kilograms of GHG [17].

In India, the fashion industry is also subject to several environmental laws. The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act of 1974, the Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act of 1981, and the

Environment Protection Act of 1986 are the primary environmental legislation that applies to the industry. The Indian government has introduced different policies to mitigate the effects of fast fashion, through zero liquid discharge norms (ZLD), zero defect, and zero effect (ZED). Sustainable fashion is an approach that changes and promotes fashion products while also ensuring their fashion and ecological integrity. The government promotes a sustainable fashion policy and also tries to educate both producers and consumers while producing and purchasing products. Sustainability is a huge challenge in the fashion industry and textile waste can be used as raw material for those value-added products. Fashion industries generate 4% of the world's waste each year, and the majority of the clothes that are produced by fast fashion are inorganic and synthetic. So, they are unable to degrade properly and these chemicals in the fabrics pollute the environment. Textile waste is largely classified as pre- and post-consumer waste. The textile and clothing industry recycles 75% of the industry-generated pre-consumer textile waste, whereas, only 15% of post-consumer waste is recycled. Figure 3 describes the hierarchy of waste management. Waste hierarchy is a framework for waste management, which has become widely adopted in recent years. According to this framework, a hierarchy is established in the order of priority of the way by which waste needs to be handled or managed to achieve the minimum environmental impact. The hierarchy sets out six levels of waste management. In descending order of preference, these six levels are (i) prevention, (ii) minimization, (iii) reuse, (iv) recycling, (v) energy recovery, and (vi) disposal.

Figure 3: Hierarchy for waste management

8. After Life of Garments

Pollution is generated from disposing of clothing in landfills and combustion plants, but the loss of value is the most important issue regarding its effects on the environment. The value of the clothing is regenerated once the manufacturing of new clothes abandons it. This has a significantly larger environmental impact than just the disposal procedure. Therefore, improving sustainability at the end of life depends on increasing the reuse and recycling rates for unwanted clothing. Garments made of polyester accumulate in landfills due to conventional PET's inability to degrade, so they last for a long time, even if they are only used for a short time [10].

9. Conclusion

To reduce textile's environmental impact, a series of changes must be incorporated. The materials used in the production of polymers and hazardous chemicals must be replaced with recycled, biobased alternatives that are safe. A smart design can also enhance circularity by encouraging manufacturing methods that use less chemicals and water. To ensure transparency, textile manufacturing companies must mandate that all textiles are labeled to identify what fibers and additives were used during manufacturing. Consumers need to know where their clothes come from and whether or not the method of production is ethical. In recent years, consumer environmental concerns have pressured companies to adopt sustainable practices.

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a significant increase in e-commerce or online shopping as people shift from in-person shopping to online due to restrictions on physical stores. Despite the opportunity e-commerce has provided for retailers and brands, concerns have also emerged about online shopping's impact on the environment, especially regarding packaging waste and transportation emissions. By offering consumers store

credit for selecting a longer expected delivery time instead of a shorter one, e-tailers can encourage consumers to choose an efficient shipping method which may reduce the packaging.

There is a lack of awareness about the environmental impact of fashion choices by common people. Educating consumers about their fashion choices' impacts on the environment is important, which can be addressed with education and awareness campaigns. These can include social media and advertising campaigns, etc.

References

- [1] K. Niinimäki, G. Peters, H. Dahlbo, P. Perry, T. Rissanen, & A. Gwilt, "The Environmental Price of Fast Fashion", *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, **1/4** (189-200), (2020). DOI:10.1038/s43017-020-0039-9
- [2] S. Rukhaya, S. Yadav, N. M. Rose, A. Grover, & D. Bisht, "A Sustainable Approach to Counter the Environmental Impact of Fast Fashion", *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. **10/8** (517-523), (2021)
- [3] S. Jung, & B. Jin, "A Theoretical Investigation of Slow Fashion: Sustainable Future of the Apparel Industry", *International Journal of Consumer Studies*. **38**, (2014). 10.1111/ijcs.12127
- [4] S. Moazzem, E. Crossin, F. Daver, F. et al. "Environmental Impact of Apparel Supply Chain and Textile Products", *Environment Development and Sustainability*, **24** (9757–9775), (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01873-4>
- [5] Roy Chowdhury AK. 'Environmental Impacts of The Textile Industry and its Assessment Through Life Cycle Assessment'. Part of the Textile Science and Clothing Technology Book Series, (2014), pp 1–39. 10.1007/978-981-287-110-7_1
- [6] S.S.A. Petroody, S. H. Hashemi, & C.A.M. Van Gestel, "Factors Affecting Microplastic Retention and Emission by a Wastewater Treatment Plant on the Southern Coast of the Caspian Sea", *Chemosphere*, **261** 128179, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128179>
- [7] E. Michaela, & S. Orna, "Fashion-conscious Consumers, Fast Fashion and The Impact of Social Media on Purchase Intention", *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, **4/3** (173), (2015). <https://doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2015.v4n3s1p173>
- [8] K. Bailey, A. Basu, & S. Sharma, "The Environmental Impacts of Fast Fashion on Water Quality: A Systematic Review", *Water*, **14/7**, (1073), (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14071073>
- [9] G.L. Oliveira, F.G. Miranda, & M.A. Dias, "Sustainable Practices in Slow and Fast Fashion Stores: What Does the Customer Perceive?" *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, **6**, 100413, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2022.100413>
- [10] C. Palacios-Mateo, Y. Van der Meer, & G. Seide, "Analysis of the polyester clothing value chain to identify key intervention points for sustainability", *Environmental Sciences Europe*, **33/2**, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-00447-x>
- [11] J.S. Weis, & F. De Falco, "Microfibers: Environmental Problems and Textile Solutions", *Microplastics*, **1** (626–639), (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3390/microplastics1040043>
- [12] S. Mishra, C.C. Rath, & A.P. Das, "Marine microfiber pollution: A Review on the Present Status and Future Challenges", *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, **140**, (188–197), (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.01.039>
- [13] R. Rathinamoorthy, T.A. Aragaw, & R. Balasaraswathi Subramanian, "Wastewater Treatment Plant Effluent and Microfiber Pollution: Focus on Industry-Specific Wastewater", *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, **29** (51211–51233), (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-20930-7>
- [14] D.M.D. Bandara, 'Impact of Social Media Advertising on Consumer Buying Behaviour: With Special Reference to the Fast Fashion Industry', *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business & Information (ICBI)*, 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3862941>
- [15] R.F. Bertram, & T. Chi, "A Study of Companies' Business Responses to Fashion E-Commerce's Environmental Impact", *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology, and Education*, **11/2** (254–264), (2018). DOI 10.1080/17543266.2017.1406541
- [16] K. Niinimäki, G. Peters, H. Dahlbo, P. Perry, T. Rissanen, & A. Gwilt, "The Environmental Price of Fast Fashion", *Nature Review | Earth & Environment*, **1** (189-200), (2020)
- [17] V. Gupta, M. Arora, & J. Minhas, 'Innovating Opportunities for Fashion Brands by Using Textile Waste for Better Fashion', In *Recycling from Waste in Fashion and Textiles: A Sustainable and Circular Economic Approach*, (Ed. P. Pandit, S. Ahmed, K. Singha, & S. Shrivastava), John Wiley & Sons, USA and Scrivener Publishing LLC, USA, (2020), pp 123-149. ISBN 978-1-119-62049-5

Figure Sources

Figure 1: P. Pandit, K. Singha, S. Shrivastava, & S. Ahmed, 'Overview on Recycling from Waste in Fashion and Textiles: A Sustainable and Circular Economic Approach', In *Recycling from Waste in Fashion and Textiles: A sustainable and Circular Economic Approach*, (Ed. P. Pandit, S. Ahmed, K. Singha, & S. Shrivastava), John Wiley & Sons, USA and Scrivener Publishing LLC, USA, (2020), p09

Figure 2: V. Gupta, M. Arora, & J. Minhas, 'Innovating Opportunities for Fashion Brands by Using Textile Waste for Better Fashion', In *Recycling from Waste in Fashion and Textiles: A sustainable and Circular Economic Approach*, (Ed.

P. Pandit, S. Ahmed, K. Singha, & S. Shrivastava), John Wiley & Sons, USA and Scrivener Publishing LLC, USA, (2020), p107

Figure 3: S. Maity, M. K. Mondal, P. Pandit, & K. Singha, 'Future Mobilizations and Paths of Waste—Towards Best Solution', In *Recycling from Waste in Fashion and Textiles: A sustainable and Circular Economic Approach*, (Ed. P. Pandit, S. Ahmed, K. Singha, & S. Shrivastava), John Wiley & Sons, USA and Scrivener Publishing LLC, USA, (2020), p323